

VOLUME-2

ISSUE № 1 2024

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL JOURNAL

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

ISSN: 2181-4279

RESEARCH
ACADEMY

1/2024

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL JOURNAL

XALQARO TA'LIM TADQIQOTLARI

ILMIY-NAZARIY JURNAL

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

Founder:
LLC "Academy of Educational
Research"

Scientific-theoretical journal
1/2024

**INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION
RESEARCH**

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The journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 20, 2023 as a mass media under the № 059 413

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FEATURES OF ORGANIZATION OF MOTOR ACTIVITY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF PRESCHOOL INSTITUTION

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10717887>

Annotation: Thus, there is much less fear of overload than underload. Physical inactivity creates conditions for abnormal physical development of children. However, in preschool educational institutions, the importance of physical activity is not taken into account enough. According to modern data, children move two times less than the age norm.

Keywords: Morning exercises, outdoor games, motor warm-up, physical education, physical education classes, outdoor games and physical exercises, recreational running, competition games.

The most accessible way to increase health potential is physical education and physical activity. Nature, through specific physiological mechanisms (in particular, fatigue), itself regulates the speed and number of movements. Thus, there is much less fear of overload than underload. Physical inactivity creates conditions for abnormal physical development of children. However, in preschool educational institutions, the importance of physical activity is not taken into account enough. According to modern data, children move two times less than the age norm.

An analysis of official documents and theoretical sources on the problem under study shows that a modern graduate of a preschool educational institution must have good health, good physical development, a high level of physical fitness, and the ability to maintain correct posture. And also to feel the need to regularly engage in physical education on one's own initiative, the desire to improve one's achievements, showing endurance, courage and initiative, to have a high (age-appropriate) performance capacity (both physical and mental), which is especially important in terms of preparing him for school. One of the ways to achieve such a level of child development is the development and use of such methods and techniques when organizing physical development activities so

that they contribute to the functional improvement of the child's body, increase its performance, make it persistent and resilient, with high protective abilities against adverse external factors. environment.

The motor mode in the preschool department includes almost all dynamic activity (motor activity) of children, both organized and independent.

When developing a rational motor regimen, it is important for each teacher not only to ensure that children's biological needs for physical activity are met, but also to provide for the rational content of physical activity, based on the optimal ratio of different types of activities, selected taking into account age and individual characteristics.

The motor activity of a preschooler should be directed and consistent with his experience, interests, desires, and functional capabilities of the body, which forms the basis of an individual approach to each child. Therefore, every teacher needs to take care of the organization of children's motor activity, its diversity, as well as the fulfillment of the main tasks and requirements for its content. The content side of the motor regime of preschoolers should be aimed at developing the mental, spiritual and physical abilities of children.

The main elements of the motor regime in the preschool department are:

1. Morning exercises - daily indoors or outdoors.

2. Outdoor games during the morning reception of children - daily 3-12 minutes.

3. Motor warm-up - daily during a long break between classes. Duration 7-10 min.

4. Physical education lesson - daily, as needed, depending on the type and content of classes. Duration 3-5 minutes.

5. Physical education classes – conducted 3 times a week by a physical development instructor (2 times in the gym and 1 time on the street).

6. Physical education classes in swimming – conducted 2 times a week by a swimming instructor.

7. Music classes - twice a week, 15-30 minutes.

8. Outdoor games and physical exercises indoors - daily with a group or subgroup of children while the children are in the preschool department.

9. Outdoor games and physical exercises during walks - daily during morning and evening walks on the sports ground, in subgroups selected taking into account the level of physical activity of children. Duration 25-30 min.

10. Health jogging – two to three times a week during a morning walk. Duration 3-7 minutes.

11. Gymnastics after naps - two to three times a week, as the children are encouraged and risen. Duration no more than 10 minutes.

12. Independent motor activity - daily, under the guidance of a teacher, indoors and outdoors. The duration depends on the individual characteristics of the children.

13. Individual work on movement development - daily during walks. Duration 12-15 minutes.

14. Hardening procedures - daily, according to individual needs.

15. Health week – twice a year.

16. Physical education – once a month, outdoors or indoors, together with peers from other groups. Duration 30-40 min.

17. Competition games – once a month

between groups in the hall or on the street.

18. Physical education and sports festivals - twice a year (winter and summer sports competitions), inside the preschool department. Duration 75-90 min.

19. Hiking trips, walks - once a quarter in the nearest forest, park, during physical education classes.

20. Participation of parents in mass physical education and recreational activities of the preschool department - during the preparation and conduct of physical education leisure activities, holidays, health week, hiking trips, attending open classes.

21. Relaxation - carried out at any suitable time with all children or individually.

22. Finger gymnastics - carried out daily individually or with a subgroup of children. Conducted at any convenient time.

23. Gymnastics for the eyes - performed daily for 3-5 minutes. at any free time, depending on the intensity of the visual load.

24. Articulation gymnastics - carried out daily individually or with a subgroup of children. Conducted at any convenient time.

25. Breathing exercises - carried out in various forms of physical education and recreational work.

Attaching particular importance to the role of physical activity in promoting the health of preschool children, it is necessary to determine priorities in the daily routine.

The first place in the motor mode of children belongs to organized physical education and recreational activities. It includes well-known types of physical activity: morning exercises, outdoor games and physical exercises during walks, physical education sessions in classes with mental stress, etc.

In order to optimize motor activity and harden children, additional types of motor activities are being introduced into the practice of our preschool department, interconnected with a complex of hardening activities, and non-traditional forms and methods of their implementation are also being introduced. Such activities include: healthy running in the air, jogging along massage paths in combination with air

baths, gymnastics after a nap, motor warm-up during the break between classes, individual work with children on the development of movements and regulation of motor activity of children on an evening walk, walks - hikes in the forest.

The second place in the motor mode of children is occupied by physical education classes - as the main form of teaching motor skills and developing optimal motor activity in children. It is recommended to conduct physical education classes at least three times a week in the morning (one outdoors).

Swimming training for children should be organized at least 2 times a week, in subgroups of 10-12 people. Only a combination of activities in the pool with a rational regime of activity and rest for children throughout the school year can help to harden and increase the physical activity of children.

The third place is given to independent motor activity that occurs on the initiative of children. It gives wide scope for the manifestation of their individual motor capabilities. Independent activity is an important source of activity and self-development of a child. Its duration depends on the individual abilities of children in motor activity.

The teacher is not a passive observer of the motor activity of children. His task in organizing this activity is to connect sedentary, inert children to the game, to slow down the hyperactive ones; switch those who were running around to play with peers, or simply invite such a child to play with you.

"Motor type" is understood as a set of individual motor characteristics inherent in a given child. Each child has his own type of motor activity. Failure to identify this type and the imposition of an unusual type of movement, according to the author, leads to the child developing a dislike for this movement, and often for physical activity in general. An increase in the amount of physical activity that is not necessary for the child and does not correspond to the type

of physical activity can lead to sharply negative consequences and become a source of long-term stress, contributing to hostility to active movements.

Currently, generally accepted criteria for assessing daily physical activity are: duration, volume and intensity. Individual differences in these indicators are so great that experts recommend conditionally dividing children into groups of high, medium and low mobility. This provides some guidelines for managing the motor activity of children. However, these characteristics are based on an average approach; the task is to determine the individual optimal motor activity of each child. In the end, greater mobility of children, depending on their individual needs for movement, can act as both optimal and excessive, and average mobility will be insufficient for someone. In this regard, the degree of mobility is more accurately characterized by the following concepts: optimal motor activity (considered as an individual norm), insufficient (hypomobility, or inactivity), excessive (hypermobility). The motor behavior of sedentary and hyperactive children coincides with the characteristics of "slow" and "hyperactive" children, which receive serious attention from physiologists, psychologists and doctors.

Forms of work on physical education with preschoolers represent a very diverse set of activities, the basis of which is motor activity based on the child's play activity. This complex includes independent motor activity and organized physical education activities. Their percentage ratio is different in groups of early, junior and senior preschool age, however, independent movements of children of all ages should account for at least 2/3 of the volume of their total motor activity. This can be explained by the fact that children are most fully realized in independent activities, which develop their creative and personal qualities. It is the least tiring of all forms of physical activity. In addition, it is in independent activity that the child most clearly demonstrates his individu-

ality, as well as the level of motor skills. The content of this activity is determined by the children themselves, but this does not mean that adults may not pay attention to it.

Organized forms of physical activity include:

- physical education classes;
- physical education and health work during the day (morning exercises, physical education sessions, outdoor games and physical exercises while walking, hardening activities, etc.);
- active recreation (physical education and holidays, health days, sports competitions, etc.);
- homework in physical education;
- individual and differentiated work (with children with deviations in physical and motor development);
- sectional classes;
- preventive and rehabilitation measures (according to the doctor's plan).

The main goal of the correct organization of the motor regime is the comprehensive physical development of children, satisfying the natural need of children for movement, improving their health, teaching children motor skills, skills and basic knowledge in physical education, creating conditions for the versatile (mental, moral, aesthetic) development of children and instilling in them the need for systematic physical exercise.

If a child is in a state of psychological comfort, then he shows genuine interest in various types of activities, the child's creative potential increases sharply and his interest covers an increasing number of objects, processes and actions.

By carefully observing children, you can quite reliably assess their psychological state during a certain period. awake, if he is clamped, constrained, it means that psychological discomfort is evident and urgent action must be taken!

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